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Corresponding Author: Prof. Barry V. Rolett,

Corresponding Author's Institution:

First Author: Barry Rolett

Order of Authors: Barry Rolett; Eric W West; John M Sinton; Radu Iovita

Abstract: The use of adze sourcing to study interaction spheres opens new perspectives on ancient Polynesian voyaging. Our work contributes to this effort by documenting the discovery and geochemical signature of the Vitaria Adze Quarry, a major adze quarry complex in the central East Polynesia core area. We present WD-XRF geochemical data for the Vitaria raw material and ethnographically collected adzes from Raivavae and Tubuai Islands, also part of the Australs. Comparison of our results with previously published artifact and source data shows that initial tool production at the Vitaria Adze Quarry coincides with the human colonization of East Polynesia. Artifacts from Rurutu were exchanged within the Australs, as well as to neighboring archipelagoes, indicating the importance of Rurutu as a node in voyaging networks spanning the East Polynesian homeland area. Large-scale tool production at the Vitaria Adze Quarry may have contributed to the rise of Vitaria District as the seat of the paramount chief and the center of power on Rurutu.

Highlights

- Sourcing of stone tools illuminates ancient East Polynesian voyaging spheres.
- X-ray fluorescence shows a unique chemical signature for the Vitaria Adze Quarry.
- Sourced adzes reveal Rurutu was a node in East Polynesian voyaging spheres by AD 1300-1400.
- The Quarry contributed to the rise of Vitaria as a chiefly ceremonial center.

1 Ancient East Polynesian Voyaging Spheres:
2 New evidence from the Vitaria Adze Quarry (Rurutu, Austral Islands)

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5 Barry V. Rolett ^{a*}, Eric W. West ^b, John M. Sinton ^c, and Radu Iovita ^d

6

7 ^a Department of Anthropology, University of Hawai'i, Manoa, Honolulu, HI USA

8 ^b Naval Facilities Engineering Command Pacific, Pearl Harbor, HI USA

9 ^c Department of Geology and Geophysics, University of Hawai'i, Manoa, Honolulu, HI, USA

10 ^d MONREPOS Archaeological Research Centre and Museum for Human Behavioral Evolution,
11 RGZM, Schloss Monrepos, Neuwied, Germany

12

13

14 * Corresponding author.

15 E-mail address: rolett@hawaii.edu (Barry V. Rolett).

16 Postal address: 2424 Maile Way, Department of Anthropology, University of Hawaii, Honolulu,
17 Hawaii USA.

18 Tel: (808) 956-7546

19 Fax: (808) 956-4893

20

21

Abstract

22

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26 Quarry, a major adze quarry complex in the central East Polynesia core area. We
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37

38

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40 fluorescence

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 The southern Cook and Austral Islands lie at the gateway to central East
44 Polynesia, an area that also includes Tahiti, the Societies, the Marquesas, and
45 Tuamotu archipelagoes. Interaction and exchange shaped the early development
46 of chiefdoms spanning this vast area. Change over time in voyaging networks is
47 explained by the *archaic interaction sphere* hypothesis, based on a model of high
48 inter-island mobility and exchange during early centuries following initial
49 colonization, with a sharp contraction of voyaging spheres after AD 1450 (e.g.,
50 Rolett, 1996, 1998, 2002; Walter, 1996a, 1998; Weisler, 2002). This two-part
51 model corresponds to a readily apparent chronological distinction in
52 archaeological sequences across central East Polynesia, with an Archaic Period
53 marked by widespread cultural continuity followed by the Classic era
54 efflorescence of distinctive and more inwardly focused chiefdoms. For the
55 southern Cooks, multiple sourcing studies trace the outline of Archaic voyaging
56 networks by drawing upon geochemical analyses of stone tools, as well as
57 evidence for inter-island transport of pearl shell and pottery (e.g. Allen and
58 Johnson, 1997; Sheppard et al., 1997; Walter, 1994, 1998). As an extension of
59 the southern Cook's chain, the Australs were important as "stepping stones" to
60 the central East Polynesia core area and beyond (Kirch, 2000) (Figure 1). Yet the
61 role of the Australs in Archaic interaction spheres remains essentially unknown.
62 Our study brings this island chain into focus by documenting the Vitaria Adze
63 Quarry on Rurutu through a collaborative archaeological and geological field
64 survey together with an integrated WD-XRF sourcing study.

65

66 The discovery and documentation of quarries provides a cornerstone for
67 geochemical adze sourcing studies. In central East Polynesia, however, there
68 are still few well-sampled quarries for which the compositional variability is
69 reliably documented (Weisler, 1997). We define a *quarry* as an archaeological
70 site displaying evidence for adze production using locally acquired raw material
71 as the source rock (Weisler and Sinton, 1997). The presence of a locally or
72 regionally significant quarry is generally marked by sets of artifacts recovered
73 from multiple locations but sharing a single distinctive geochemical signature. An
74 example of this pattern is displayed by studies focused on the Marquesas, where
75 up to 25% or more of adzes from individual site assemblages can be matched to
76 the Eiao Quarry located in the northern Marquesas (McAlister, 2011; Rolett,
77 1998; Rolett et al., 1997). By contrast, the absence of such a pattern in Cook
78 Islands sourcing studies suggests that adze rock derives from various dispersed
79 locations, mainly from within the Cooks, without intensive exploitation of specific
80 geological sources (Sheppard et al., 1997; Walter and Sheppard, 2001). Most
81 adze rock was likely obtained through casual procurement, as in collecting river
82 cobbles; the geochemical evidence does not indicate that “any particular point
83 source in the Cook Islands was systematically ‘quarried’ for adze stone” (Walter
84 and Sheppard, 2001:594). Current geochemical data for the Society Islands
85 tentatively shows a raw material procurement pattern more similar to that
86 documented for the Marquesas, but actual locations of the geological sources, as
87 well as locations of the adze workshops and quarries, have not yet been

88 identified (Kahn et al., 2013). A single quarry (Tanataetea), with evidence for
89 extraction of dyke stone for adze production, is recorded for Tubuai in the
90 Australs (Hermann, 2013), however there is no evidence yet that Tanataetea
91 adzes were transported to other islands.

92

93 This overview points to considerable advances in the use of adze sourcing to
94 define interaction spheres, while also identifying an important limitation. The
95 scarcity of quarries for which actual locations are known, across the entire central
96 East Polynesia core area, complicates the definitive point sourcing of adzes. It
97 prevents us from addressing questions concerning the nature of the geological
98 formations exploited (e.g., lava flows or dike swarms), the geochemical variability
99 of these sources, the methods employed for procuring raw material, and the
100 extent and scale of adze production zones. Moreover, without knowledge of the
101 locations of procurement and production zones, our understanding of quarries as
102 part of the cultural landscape (Cooney, 2011) also remains an open question.

103

104 Thus, it is notable that more than five decades ago over 300 adze fragments and
105 preforms were surface collected in the Vitaria district of Rurutu, some in direct
106 association with lithic workshops (Kellum and Garanger, 1964; Verin, 1969).

107 Although it seemed likely that these workshops and adzes represent a quarry,
108 prior research did not attempt to physically locate the procurement zones. With
109 this in mind, we designed and carried out a collaborative archaeological and
110 geological field survey of Rurutu. Our primary goal was to locate the specific

111 geological source from which Vitaria raw material was extracted, to test the
112 geochemical variability within procurement zones, and to compare the chemical
113 composition of the source rock with that of artifacts collected from the associated
114 workshops and surrounding area. After locating and sampling the procurement
115 zones, we attempted to establish basic parameters for understanding the cultural
116 context of the Vitaria quarry complex. We also sought to address the problem of
117 the geographical extent of movement of artifacts from the quarry. Ideally, this
118 would be done by sourcing adzes from controlled excavations on neighboring
119 islands in the Australs archipelago. However, given the current lack of such
120 artifact assemblages, we analyzed nine Peabody Essex Museum adzes surface
121 collected on Raivavae and Tubuai, the two islands closest to Rurutu. We also
122 reviewed the literature of geochemical data for analyzed artifacts collected in the
123 central East Polynesia core area, to search for specimens that match the
124 composition of raw material from Vitaria and other Rurutu sources.

125

126 **2. Regional setting**

127 *2.1. Cultural setting*

128 The Vitaria Adze Quarry, consisting of workshops and raw material procurement
129 zones, is directly associated with one of the most highly nucleated chiefly centers
130 in Polynesia. The site complex covers a strip of coastal plain at the foot of
131 makatea (uplifted limestone) slopes descending from Rurutu's volcanic interior
132 (Figure 2). Local traditions state that Vitaria's rise to prominence as the seat of
133 the paramount chief occurred well after initial settlement of Rurutu, following an

134 epic clash in which Vitaria vanquished its foes (Seabrook, 1938). Vitaria's
135 archaeological remains reveal a remarkably well-preserved and architecturally-
136 uniform complex of elaborately paved house sites (Verin, 1969). A focal point is
137 the Te'utamatea area, which includes chiefly residences, a ceremonial meeting
138 ground, and Marae Tararoa, described in traditions as the burial place for eight
139 chiefs and one of the most revered religious sites on Rurutu (Verin, 1969:122)
140 (Figure 3). The meeting ground is distinguished by massive upright stones made
141 of columnar basalt (Figure 4). The largest of these, ritually named Teari'i Uira,
142 measures 1.9 m in length and was the paramount chief's backrest stone (Verin,
143 1969:118). In direct proximity to the meeting ground and *marae* is the nearly 70
144 m long *'are 'ari'oi*, which served as a barracks and training ground for warriors
145 (Verin, 1969). Significantly, Vitaria's quarry and adze production zone fall
146 squarely within the heart of this chiefly complex. Marae Tararoa lies only 20
147 meters from the slope where exposed residual boulders of volcanic rock supplied
148 raw material for the adze industry.

149

150 The Vitaria complex dates mainly to the Classic Period, as demonstrated by
151 chronologically-diagnostic artifacts, and with the concurrence of genealogical
152 data (Verin, 1969). The adze assemblage (Verin, 1969:175-190) consists entirely
153 of tanged triangular cross-section forms, typical of the Classic era. Fishhooks
154 from the Vitaria excavations (Verin, 1969:214-227) are also good time markers.
155 Nearly all of them are made of *Turbo* shell, diagnostic of the Classic era, in
156 contrast to the dominantly pearl shell Archaic fishhook assemblages of the Cooks

157 and Australs (Boltt, 2008; Walter and Campbell, 1996). While the specific
158 radiocarbon chronology for the Australs Classic Period is not well defined, we
159 know that this era developed after AD 1450 and likely reached it's peak during
160 the eighteenth century (Boltt, 2008).

161

162 Both Verin (1969: 121-122) and our team located surface remains of adze
163 manufacturing workshops at the Vitaria ceremonial complex. Verin (1969:175)
164 noted he could easily have collected more than one thousand adze preforms
165 from the site surface. He was also the first to recognize the significance of adze
166 workshops located on the *marae* grounds:

167 "A rather unusual role of the *marae* lies in the use of the immediate surrounding
168 area (north and south) for adze production. Specialists involved in this activity
169 undoubtedly were required to follow certain religious restrictions, because their
170 work on the grounds of a religious site could not have been by accident" (Verin,
171 1969:122, translated from French).

172 Thus Classic Period adze production at Vitaria, one of the few known major
173 quarries in central East Polynesia, was set in a sacred context.

174

175 *2.2. Environmental setting*

176 Rurutu is geologically remarkable in being constructed of two volcanic units of
177 strongly contrasting age, separated by 100 m of uplifted limestone. The older unit
178 (Rurutu Old) was emplaced 12.7-12.1 Ma, mainly in a shallow marine
179 environment, and it formed alkali basaltic pillow lava flows and breccias that

180 eventually became subaerial (Maury et al., 2000). Overlaying the early volcanics
181 are limestones rich in coral debris and other fossils, which indicate deposition
182 ~10.5 – 6.5 Ma (Bourrouilh-Le Jan, 1984; Maury et al., In press). The limestones
183 make steep makatea cliffs that became deeply incised by erosion, as well as
184 dissolution from surface waters, after the island became elevated above
185 sealevel. Following uplift a much younger volcanic series (Rurutu Recent) was
186 emplaced ~1.1 – 1.0 Ma (Guille et al., 1998). The younger series is chemically
187 distinct from the earlier volcanics and mainly consists of basanites and tephrites.
188 The younger volcanics unconformably drape older topography, forming ~10 m
189 thick flows that commonly display columnar jointing (Maury et al., 2000). The
190 Vitaria Quarry is located within the younger volcanic sequence, exploiting a thick
191 flow that drapes the slope immediately inland from Te‘autamatea (Figure 2).

192

193 The southern Cooks and Australs form a linear chain of geologically diverse
194 landforms ranging from coral atolls to makatea and high volcanic islands. Rurutu,
195 one of the largest of the Australs, has considerable resources of fine-grained
196 volcanic rock and multiple sites representing local adze production. Among the
197 neighboring islands, Tubuai is also an abundant source of volcanic rock, with at
198 least one adze quarry, the Tanataetea complex (Hermann, 2013). By contrast,
199 the smaller islands of Raivavae and Rimatara have little or no naturally occurring
200 tool-quality volcanic rock. Rimatara has no exposed outcrops of volcanic rock
201 (Turner and Jarrad, 1982:203), while Raivavae offers some volcanic rock but
202 fine-grained material is scarce. Although there is no local evidence for adze

203 production on Raivavae, a survey by Edmundo Edwards yielded numerous
204 finished adzes, suggesting that at least some of these were acquired through
205 inter-island exchange (Edwards, 2003:161). In the Cooks, Rarotonga, the only
206 sizable high volcanic island, has vast stone resources but no known quarries.
207 Mangaia bears evidence for two possible quarries, but no workshops have been
208 located and the distribution of adzes made of Mangaian raw material was highly
209 localized (Sheppard et al., 1997:103; Weisler et al., 1994). Aitutaki has a number
210 of small local sources (Allen and Johnson, 1997) but volcanic rock is nearly
211 absent on Ma'uke and Atiu (Sheppard et al., 1997:103).

212

213 **3. Materials and methods**

214 The Vitaria adze workshops were first recorded by Pierre Verin during his 1960s
215 study of the Te'utamatea chiefly residence and ceremonial complex (Verin,
216 1969). Information collected from local informants provided Verin with names and
217 genealogical histories for some of the key structures. During our one week
218 survey in 2000, we found Te'utamatea under the care of Viriamu Teuruarii,
219 direct descendant of the last paramount chief of Rurutu. The Teuruarii family
220 lives at Te'utamatea, keeps the area well-cleared of vegetation, and the
221 archaeological complex is remarkably intact. Guided by Viriamu, we easily
222 located and identified the individual structures mapped by Verin. Among these,
223 the most relevant are those directly associated with the Vitaria workshops (Figure
224 3).

225

226 Verin located workshops at the heart of the Vitaria ceremonial complex, adjacent
227 to Marae Tararoa and the chiefs' meeting ground (Verin, 1969:121-122, 129).

228 There are still localized surface scatters of debitage and adze preforms
229 throughout Te'autamatea, which we surveyed to collect a series of 27 artifacts
230 (Figures 2, 3). Among these, seven specimens (five adze preforms and two
231 debitage flakes) were selected for chemical analysis (Table 1). The specimens
232 selected for analysis are artifacts considered representative of the Te'autamatea
233 collection as a whole.

234

235 The closest source of tool quality stone is the makatea slope rising from the
236 coastal plain to the volcanic flows of the island's interior. Throughout the Vitaria
237 district, massive boulders of tephrite (or nepheline hawaiite), eroding from the
238 makatea slope, provide an abundant source of raw material (Figure 5). Our
239 survey of Te'autamatea and areas to the north also revealed evidence for
240 primary acquisition of the raw material. Raw material was procured by removing
241 large flakes, up to 30 cm in length, from boulders along the base of the makatea
242 slope and at low elevations. Primary flakes are found in surface contexts
243 throughout the region, together with shaped blocks of raw material. Adze
244 production zones for the shaping of preforms are concentrated on the coastal
245 plain. For geochemical analysis, we selected two cores, two primary flakes, one
246 preform, and two geological samples from boulders in the Vitaria area north of
247 Te'autamatea (Figure 2).

248

249 The coastal plain south of Te'utamatea is also scattered with adze workshops.
250 Purearea stream cuts across the coastal plain less than .5 km southeast of
251 Marae Tararoa (Figure 2). The coastal plain is about 100 m wide at this point. We
252 surveyed stream profiles from the beach to the base of the makatea slope, and
253 about midway we collected two adze preforms and a large primary flake from the
254 northwest profile. These artifacts were found *in situ*, exposed in a buried cultural
255 deposit ~1.5 - 2 m below the adjacent ground surface of the coastal plain. Both
256 preforms from the subsurface deposit are quadrangular types diagnostic of the
257 Archaic tradition. These two Archaic adzes, and a third preform from the nearby
258 makatea slope, were analyzed for comparison with other Vitaria samples.

259

260 During their 1962 survey, Kellum, Garanger, and Verin were guided by Martin
261 Brunor, an American fluent in the Rurutu dialect and with extensive experience in
262 French Polynesia. Brunor assembled an important collection of Austral Islands
263 artifacts for the Peabody Essex Museum, adding to it over more than three
264 decades (Brunor, 1969). During the survey with Kellum and colleagues, Brunor
265 made his own separate collection of 263 adze preforms and finished adzes, all
266 from Vitaria and now housed in the Peabody Essex Museum. We selected five
267 representative specimens (four preforms and one finished adze) for geochemical
268 analysis (Table 1). The 1962 survey also identified adze workshops in the Unaa
269 district, at the north tip of the island, but these are mentioned only in passing and
270 the exact locations are not recorded (Kellum and Garanger, 1964:33; Verin,
271 1969:133). Since that time, construction of the airport has destroyed most of the

272 Unaa archaeological landscape. We briefly explored part of the undisturbed area,
273 where we collected two samples (one large primary flake, one geological
274 specimen) for analysis.

275

276 Whole-rock samples for X-ray fluorescence analysis were broken into ~1 cm
277 chips using a WC hydraulic splitter, hand picked to remove obvious alteration
278 and rinds, and crushed in a WC swing mill. Major and trace element
279 concentrations were measured with the University of Hawai'i Siemens 303 AS
280 automated x-ray fluorescence spectrometry system, using methods described in
281 Sinton et al. (2005) and Eason and Sinton (2006). Major elements were
282 determined on fused glass discs, following methods similar to those of Norrish
283 and Hutton (1977). Trace elements were analyzed on pressed powder pellets.
284 Peak intensities for trace elements were corrected for backgrounds, line
285 interferences and matrix absorption using methods similar to Chappell (1992).
286 Corrected intensities were calibrated against a wide range of natural rock
287 standards. Accuracy and precision data for the UH system are reported in Sinton
288 et al. (2005).

289

290 Were adzes produced on Rurutu exported to other islands? The answer lies in
291 sourcing artifacts from sites elsewhere in the Australs and beyond. As a step in
292 this effort, we analyzed the composition of nine additional adzes housed in the
293 Peabody Essex Museum. These artifacts consist mostly of finished, polished
294 adzes (complete specimens and fragments) collected on Raivavae and Tubuai

295 (Table 1). They were acquired for the Peabody by anthropologist Donald
296 Marshall, during field work in 1955 and 1957-58 when he was accompanied by F.
297 Alan Seabrook, a local expert on the Australs (Marshall, 1961). In selecting the
298 nine adzes for compositional analysis, we chose artifacts that are representative
299 of Marshall's collection and which could be sampled (using a diamond core drill
300 bit) without damaging surfaces important in terms of either aesthetics or artifact
301 technology.

302

303 **4. Results**

304 *4.1. Sourcing protocols and characterization of the Vitaria quarry signature*

305 Two different but complementary approaches have proven effective in using
306 major and trace element chemical data for the sourcing of archaeological
307 artifacts in Pacific Island environments. One approach, essentially exploratory,
308 involves the analysis of large numbers of artifacts with the goal of identifying
309 sources within a region for which there are few, if any, documented quarries. This
310 approach employs a combination of geological or statistical methods to group
311 artifacts into separate provenance environments (e.g. Sheppard et al., 1997;
312 Kahn et al., 2013). In regions with archaeologically "undiscovered" quarries, the
313 exploratory approach can reveal clusters of artifacts made of chemically similar
314 raw material, making it possible to recognize a source without actually identifying
315 its physical location.

316

317 The second approach differs in that the goal is to assign, or match, artifacts to
318 geochemically-defined sources. These may include both quarries with *known*
319 *locations*, as well as others with *unknown locations* identified through the
320 exploratory approach. Matching artifacts to specific sources is usually achieved
321 by direct comparison of the compositions, based on a selection of major and/or
322 trace elements, or the ratios of certain elements. Isotopic ratios can provide
323 additional constraints, especially for those cases where there is overlap among
324 the major and trace element chemical signatures of separate sources (e.g.
325 Collerson and Weisler 1997). Protocols for the artifact assignment approach
326 focus on certain elements found to be the most effective in source discrimination.
327 Among the major elements, these include SiO_2 , TiO_2 , K_2O , and P_2O_5 (Weisler
328 and Sinton, 1997). The underlying premise of the matching approach, as stated
329 by Weisler and Sinton, is: "If two rocks have identical compositions for all
330 elements, within analytical uncertainties, then it is highly probable that they
331 indeed are from the same volcano and probably the same lava flow or dyke (that
332 is source)" (1997:180).

333

334 To determine the chemical signature of the Vitaria quarry rock and to match
335 artifacts to it, we developed a modified version of the sourcing protocol proposed
336 by Weisler and Sinton (1997). First, we compared the composition of four
337 geological samples and 20 artifacts, all from the Vitaria adze production zone.
338 The geological samples represent four separate boulders eroding from a lava
339 flow partially exposed on the slope above the Vitaria coastal plain, in an area

340 where large primary flakes provide direct evidence for raw material procurement.
341 The artifacts, all of which were collected at the quarry complex, consist of primary
342 flakes, cores, debitage, adze performs, and a single complete polished adze.
343 Results show that the geological samples, together with 18 of the artifacts, are
344 highly similar in composition (Table 2). These geological samples and artifacts
345 form a well-defined cluster on geochemical variation diagrams (Figure 6). Two of
346 the artifacts (RUR-24, RUR-46) are notable outliers, indicating that some of the
347 raw material used at Vitaria workshops actually derives from other locations
348 (Table 3, Figure 6). We selected the four geological samples and the 18 artifacts
349 that cluster with them to calculate the mean composition and quarry signature of
350 the Vitaria source (Table 2).

351

352 A close correspondence between the artifact and geological compositions
353 indicates that the source material is local to Vitaria, and it further suggests a
354 highly selective choice of raw material used in adze production. The Vitaria
355 source rock is very fine grained and devoid of vesicles; it contains <1% olivine
356 crystals ~1 mm in size. The source rock is therefore texturally homogeneous
357 making it highly suitable for adze production. It may also be significant that the
358 exploited flow represents an extreme in composition for Rurutu, comprising the
359 high-SiO₂ differentiated limit of the Rurutu younger series of volcanics (see
360 Figure 6). Sheppard and colleagues hypothesize that high SiO₂ rock offers
361 desirable properties, including high fracture toughness and predictable fracture

362 during flaking, selected for in the procurement of raw material for adze
363 manufacture (Sheppard et al., 2001:358-359).

364

365 Although we believe that only one lava flow was actively worked at the Vitaria
366 quarry, the flow is slightly variable in composition. Thus, it is necessary to
367 evaluate the compositional range of the quarry source. Deviations from the
368 mean composition can arise from analytical precision and/or primary magmatic
369 processes. The latter are indicated by systematic covariations with MgO, as
370 shown by the linear array of the Vitaria cluster in Figure 6b, consistent with a
371 single lava flow's liquid line of descent. To estimate the magnitude of the
372 variation, we use the standard deviations from the mean calculation, which in
373 most cases are greater than the analytical precision (see Sinton and Sinoto
374 (1997) for precision estimates for the UH XRF). In rare cases where the standard
375 deviation is less than our estimated precision, we use the actual precision
376 estimate in place of the deviation from the mean.

377

378 The Vitaria quarry signature then can be characterized as the mean \pm the
379 uncertainty, where uncertainty is either one standard deviation from the mean or
380 analytical uncertainty, whichever is greater. The quarry signature is depicted
381 graphically in Figure 7, which also plots three of the Peabody adzes collected on
382 Raivavae and Tubuai for comparison. All values are normalized to the mean
383 Vitaria source composition; uncertainty bounds on the shaded Vitaria source
384 composition are calculated as $(\text{mean} + 1s)/\text{mean}$ and $(\text{mean} - 1s)/\text{mean}$. The
385 mean source composition together with the uncertainty bounds comprise the

386 quarry signature. In addition, Figure 7 illustrates the variation uncertainty among
387 different major element oxides and trace elements. Certain elements identified as
388 unreliable indicators, including MnO and Na₂O, are not plotted for the quarry
389 signature. MnO occurs in low abundance and it shows too little variation to be
390 meaningful. Na₂O is also among the least reliable of the major element oxides. It
391 is the highest (like 5%) for analytic error and it also tends to be variable among
392 different laboratories (Sinton and Sinoto, 1997). Figure 7 shows results for those
393 elements that we think are reliable discriminants for the Vitaria source.

394

395 Compositional data for an unknown artifact can be compared with the quarry
396 signature, as in Figure 7. Two Peabody adzes collected on Raivavae (E36497,
397 E36496) have compositions that agree with the Vitaria source within uncertainty
398 for all elements. These Raivavae adzes are therefore chemically
399 indistinguishable from the Vitaria source. One cannot preclude the possibility that
400 a chemically identical (indistinguishable) rock occurs naturally somewhere else,
401 but this is unlikely and at present there are no archeologically important rocks
402 from the Pacific that cannot be distinguished by careful analysis. The simplest
403 explanation for this match is that the Raivavae adzes are made of raw material
404 derived from Vitaria. By contrast, an adze from Tubuai (E36447) is shown as an
405 example of a misfit with the Vitaria source composition (Figure 7). Clearly, this
406 adze is made of rock from a source other than Vitaria.

407

408 As illustrated in Figure 7, the two Raivavae adzes sourced to Vitaria match the
409 Vitaria quarry signature for both major and trace elements. We emphasize this
410 point to show that in this sourcing case study (and based on our experience, in
411 others as well) major element data analysis is a robust, as well as cost and labor-
412 efficient method for chemical characterization. Despite recent arguments by
413 Weisler et al. (2013) and Hermann (2013) that reliable characterization requires
414 the analysis of trace elements and Sr-Nd-Pb isotopes, in addition to major
415 elements, our study demonstrates that this is not always the case.

416

417 We return briefly to the two data outliers among the artifacts collected at Vitaria.
418 One of these, RUR-46, is adebitage flake from the adze production zone near
419 the Te'utamatea meeting ground. The composition is quite distinct from that of
420 the other Vitaria artifacts, but it is nevertheless consistent with a Rurutu origin
421 (Table 3). The second outlier, RUR-24, a primary flake measuring 25 cm by 20
422 cm, is from an unknown source distinguished by higher SiO₂ values than those
423 recorded for any analyzed lavas from Rurutu. Among the existing Austral Islands
424 data (Maury et al., In press), broadly similar compositions are known only from
425 Rapa. Thus, apparently at least some of the rock worked at Vitaria was acquired
426 from sources elsewhere on Rurutu, and also likely from a different island.

427

428 *4.2. Sourcing of the Peabody Essex Museum adzes*

429 Seven of the Peabody Museum adzes were collected on Raivavae, where the
430 scarcity of tool quality rock likely stimulated exchange with other islands

431 (Edwards 2003:161). As discussed above and depicted in Figure 7, two of the
432 Raivavae adzes are chemically indistinguishable from Vitaria, indicating that they
433 were fashioned from raw material most likely derived from Vitaria. Two other
434 Peabody adzes collected on Raivavae may also derive from Rurutu sources.
435 Compositions of adzes E-33006 and E-36512, closely match data for the
436 Na'a'iroa and Ta'urama sources (Table 4, Figure 6). The Taurama and Na'a'iroa
437 compositions plot with the field of recent volcanics on Figure 6 but they are more
438 mafic than the Vitaria tephrites. They are also richer in normative olivine and can
439 be classified as basanite.

440

441 Both the Na'a'iroa and Ta'urama sources were discovered and recorded by Bollt
442 (2008) in the south of the island. The Na'a'iroa chemical signature is based on
443 data for a single geological specimen and two debitage flakes collected at an
444 adze production zone, with matching artifacts from the early Peva deposits (Bollt
445 2008: 205, 207). The Ta'urama signature is based on data for a single geological
446 specimen collected in an area with no observed lithic workshops (Bollt 2008:
447 208). Two artifacts excavated by Bollt (an adze preform and a debitage flake)
448 tentatively match the Ta'urama geological specimen (Bollt 2008: 209). It is
449 important to note, however, that data for both Na'a'iroa and Ta'urama are limited,
450 neither source has been studied in detail, and there is some overlap with recently
451 recorded Tubuai sources (Hermann 2013). In sum, based on current evidence,
452 the compositions of Peabody adzes E-33006 and E-36512 collected on Raivavae

453 are consistent with both artifacts having been acquired through interisland
454 exchange from Rurutu or Tubuai.

455

456 The apparent frequency of imported adzes on Raivavae, and the scarcity of high
457 quality local rock on that island, are significant in light of information shared with
458 Capt. James Cook by the Society Islands savant Tupaia. According to Tupaia,
459 who possessed knowledge of more than 80 islands (Forster, 1996:310),
460 Raivavae was a point of origin for quality adzes shipped to the Societies (Finney,
461 1994:289, 347-348; Forster, 1996:315). Thus, our findings together with Tupaia's
462 observations, suggest Raivavae may have served as a stepping stone in the
463 transport of Rurutu adzes to the Society Islands.

464

465 In addition to Vitaria, Na'a'iroa, and Ta'urama, there is likely at least one
466 additional source on Rurutu, located at Una'a. Two Una'a adze production zones
467 were noted in the 1960s (Kellum and Garanger 1964:33), at the far north of
468 Rurutu in an area vastly transformed by later construction of the airport runway.
469 We collected two reference samples (Table 3) in this area, however, locating the
470 Una'a source may be impossible due to the airport disturbance. A number of
471 debitage flakes from Archaic era deposits of Rurutu's Peva site fit the tentatively
472 established Una'a signature (Bollt 2008:199, 205-206) but none of the Peabody
473 adzes match this source. Una'a tephrites also are within the Rurutu Recent
474 volcanics, but with higher MgO and lower SiO₂ than the Vitaria source lava.

475

476 Two Raivavae adzes are made of benmoreite (Figure 6), a rock type known
477 within the Australs only from Rapa and Raivavae (Maury et al., 2013; In press).
478 Both Raivavae and Rapa geochemical data define trends in total alkalis versus
479 SiO_2 that range from hawaiite to trachyte (Figure 6), i.e., at lower total alkalis than
480 the tephrite to phonolite trend that is characteristic of Tubuai. Thus, compositions
481 for the two Raivavae benmoreite adzes are generally consistent with local
482 Raivavae sources, although the possibility of a Rapa origin cannot be precluded
483 based on presently available data. One of the Raivavae adzes (E-36510) is a
484 preform fashioned from an expediently worked piece of columnar stone, which
485 further supports the hypothesis of a local source. The second preform (E-36509)
486 is broadly similar to E-36510 in composition. Finally, there is little that can be said
487 about Sample E-36500, also collected on Raivavae. The composition of this adze
488 lies near the basalt/basanite boundary, outside the Rurutu Recent and Rurutu
489 Old sequences, and a Rurutu source is therefore unlikely. The composition is
490 consistent with a local Raivavae source, but the raw material could also be from
491 Tubuai or even Rapa based on its chemistry.

492

493 Tubuai, situated midway between Rurutu and Raivavae, is the largest island in
494 the Australs and its mountainous core offers large quantities of fine-grained
495 volcanic rock suitable for adze production. Tubuai is notable for the Tanataetea
496 quarry complex, consisting of adze workshops and a dike that was systematically
497 mined for raw material (Hermann 2013). The geochemical data for Tanataetea is
498 based on two quarry samples (one geological, one archaeological) and three

499 chemically similar artifacts from the nearby Atiahara archaeological site
500 (Hermann 2013:403). Both of the two Peabody adzes collected on Tubuai have
501 basanitic compositions consistent with geochemically recorded Tubuai lava
502 flows. One adze (E-36447) closely matches Tanataetea (Figure 6). The second
503 (E-36449) does not match any known source; basanites are broadly distributed
504 among the Austral and Cook Islands, but given that the adze was collected on
505 Tubuai, that is the most likely place of origin.

506

507 **5. Discussion**

508 *5.1. Archaic era links between Rurutu, the Cook Islands, and beyond*

509 Our study documents Rurutu's Vitaria adze quarry and presents evidence for the
510 exchange of Vitaria adze rock to a neighboring island (Figure 8). Now that the
511 Vitaria quarry signature is established, future investigations will surely bring forth
512 a better understanding of Vitaria rock as a proxy for ancient voyaging spheres.
513 As a step in this direction, here we look at Rurutu in the broader context of
514 Austral Islands voyaging spheres. The emerging archaeological record reveals
515 that central East Polynesian interaction spheres carried Rurutu adze rock as far
516 as the Tuamotus (Figure 8) (Collerson and Weisler, 2007). These islands, which
517 consist entirely of coral atolls and uplifted limestone formations, are completely
518 devoid of volcanic rock, and considerable numbers of stone adzes from the
519 Marquesas and Societies were exchanged to the Tuamotus (Weisler, 1998). A
520 single adze (C2365) collected on the Tuamotu island of Aratika was sourced to
521 Rurutu. Like the Peabody adzes, the Aratika adze was surface collected and the

522 archaeological context is unknown. It was analyzed and sourced to Rurutu by
523 Collerson and Weisler (2007) mainly on radiogenic isotope data, which strongly
524 support the Rurutu attribution. Major and trace element data for C2365 do not
525 match Vitaria or other known Rurutu sources but the composition is within the
526 fields for Rurutu Recent volcanics.

527

528 In light of this evidence for long-distance exchange, we draw attention to two
529 Cook Islands artifacts that may also derive from Rurutu (Figure 8). The artifacts
530 consist of an adze preform and a core of raw material excavated from a
531 fourteenth century deposit of the Anai'o site on Mauke, 670 km northwest of
532 Rurutu (Walter, 1990). The preform is an untanged quadrangular type
533 characteristic of the Archaic era (AD 1300-1400). Both artifacts are directly
534 associated with a structure interpreted as a stone working specialist's residence
535 (Walter, 1990:65, 1996). The preform lay amidst a dense scatter of lithic
536 debitage, while the core, which weighs nearly 2 kg, was cached nearby in a pit
537 beneath the house floor (Walter, 1990:65).

538

539 The Anai'o adze preform and core were analyzed for major elements only. Based
540 on limited available geochemical data (including two Mauke geological
541 specimens) for the Cooks and Australs at that time, Sheppard et al. (1997:94)
542 hypothesized the preform and core consist of local Mauke stone. However,
543 recent studies show the artifact compositions are also broadly similar to
544 basanites naturally occurring on Rurutu and Tubuai, as well as Mauke (Maury et

545 al., In press). Specifically, the new evidence indicates the Anai'o adze preform
546 and core are closer in major element composition to the Rurutu Na'a'iroa source
547 than to the Mauke geological specimens, especially in TiO_2 , FeO , CaO , and P_2O_5
548 (Table 4).

549

550 The context of the Anai'o adze preform and cached core is revealing. First,
551 caching suggests special treatment for a high value raw material. This is
552 consistent with the treatment of imported adzes discovered in a cache on
553 Rarotonga (Walter and Sheppard, 1996). Temporal context is also significant, as
554 the artifacts date to a period of systematic voyaging within the Archaic-era East
555 Polynesian regional homeland (e.g. Rolett, 1996; 2002; Walter, 1996a). In terms
556 of site location, it is noteworthy that Anai'o faces a pass in Mauke's fringing reef,
557 providing an optimum setting for inter-island seafaring (Walter, 1996b:83-84).
558 Finally, there are no known adze quarries on Mauke and naturally occurring fine-
559 grained tool quality rock is scarce (Sheppard et al., 1997). By contrast, Rurutu
560 was a major center for adze production. On these grounds, and because the
561 major element composition of the Anai'o artifacts more closely matches Rurutu's
562 Na'a'iroa source than the Mauke geological specimens, we suggest a Rurutu
563 origin is more likely than a Mauke one. It cannot be proven, however, without
564 further analyses (e.g. trace elements and isotopes) of the Anai'o artifacts.

565

566 Evidence for Rurutu's exchange networks fits the emerging broader pattern of
567 early East Polynesian interaction spheres. Within the Australs and Cooks,

568 support for the archaic interaction sphere model includes: 1) adzes discovered
569 on Mangaia and Rarotonga but sourced to Samoa (Weisler and Kirch, 1996;
570 Walter and Sheppard, 1996); 2) pottery discovered on Mauke but sourced to
571 Tonga (Walter and Dickinson, 1989); and 3) the archaeological discovery on
572 Tubuai of an adze imported from the Marquesas (Hermann, 2013). Finally, we
573 note that a Rurutu source for the Anai'o core implies blocks of raw material, not
574 only adze preforms, were exchanged between Polynesian islands.

575

576 *5.2. The chronology of adze production and exchange*

577 Initial colonization of the Southern Cooks and Australs occurred no earlier than
578 ca. AD 1200-1300 according to a recent revision of the East Polynesian
579 radiocarbon chronology (Wilmshurst et al., 2010). This scenario is consistent with
580 evidence from Rurutu's Peva site, which revealed a late thirteenth century to
581 early fifteenth century Archaic deposit containing fossil remains of extinct fauna
582 suggesting a founder settlement (Boltt, 2008; Steadman and Boltt, 2010). The
583 same deposit yielded adzes sourced to Vitaria (Boltt, 2008:199), implying that
584 discovery of the Vitaria Quarry occurred during the Archaic period, perhaps a
585 century or less after initial colonization. The earliest chronological evidence from
586 the Vitaria site itself is a single uncalibrated date of 900 ± 90 for a deposit located
587 well beneath the pavements and foundations of the Classic Period architectural
588 complex. The dated sample (Gak 448) consists of charcoal from an earth oven
589 about 80 cm below surface (Verin, 1969:90,92,307). This sample was analyzed
590 during the same year (1964), and by the same laboratory (Gakushuin), that

591 produced a separate suite of Archaic era Marquesan radiocarbon dates
592 examined by Anderson and Sinoto (2002) and considered to be accurate.
593
594 The well-established Duff (1977) typology of East Polynesian adzes offers further
595 insight for understanding the chronology of Rurutu adze production and
596 exchange. Kellum, Garanger, and Verin surface collected 314 adze fragments
597 and preforms, in addition to 11 complete adzes during their survey of the Vitaria
598 complex (Kellum and Garanger, 1964). All of these are triangular in cross-section
599 (Duff Type 3), as is typical of Classic era adzes, in contrast to the quadrangular
600 adzes prevalent during the Archaic (Bollt, 2008; Verin, 1969:169). Thus, there is
601 no doubt that adze production at the Vitaria Quarry was a large scale operation
602 during the Classic Period. However, our Vitaria preforms from the Purearea
603 stream profile are quadrangular types represented almost exclusively in Archaic
604 era sites. Both specimens bear the distinctive Vitaria chemical signature. This
605 finding, together with support from the Peva radiocarbon dates, indicates that
606 Rurutu adze production began during the Archaic, centuries before the
607 emergence of Vitaria as a Classic Period chiefly ceremonial complex.

608

609 *5.3. The role of the quarry in Vitaria's rise to prominence*

610 Te'autamatea, at the center of Vitaria's Classic Period ceremonial complex, is
611 described as urban-like because of the carefully planned, tightly-spaced layout of
612 houses (Verin, 1969:168). There are around one hundred residential structures,
613 such that the population density and the lack of land suitable for irrigated taro

614 made Vitaria dependent upon other districts for food (Seabrook, 1938:53-54).
615 While poor in resources, Vitaria also lacks a pass through the broad coastal
616 fringe reef. The nearest place for launching and landing sailing canoes is Avera
617 Bay, some 2 km south of Vitaria. In this context, the value of Vitaria stone and
618 adzes may have contributed to the rise of the Vitaria's extraordinary urban
619 complex and chiefly center. We suggest this as a plausible hypothesis, given the
620 high-quality, abundance, and easy access of the adze rock, the large scale of
621 production, and evidence presented here for the inter-island exchange of Vitaria
622 adzes. The direct association of adze workshops with Marae Tararoa lends
623 additional support, by showing that adze production was under the control of
624 Vitaria's elite rulers.

625

626

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637

638

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857

858 **Figure captions**

859

860 Figure 1. Location of the Austral Islands in the central East Polynesian core area.

861

862 Figure 2. Location of the Vitaria District on Rurutu, Austral Islands.

863

864 Figure 3. Map of the Te'utamatea (Vitaria District, Rurutu) chiefly center,
865 showing location of the Vitaria Adze Quarry raw material procurement zones and
866 workshops in relation to culturally significant sites. Identification of the oval-ended

867 houses (Teh 3,5,6), meeting ground, and Marae Tararoa is based on Verin
868 (1969).

869

870 Figure 4. View of the chiefs' meeting ground at Te'autamatea. The upright stones
871 of columnar basalt served as backrests for the paramount chief and other elites.
872 The largest stone (named Teari'i Uira) was the paramount chief's backrest (Verin
873 1969:118). Photo by B. Rolett (June, 2000).

874

875 Figure 5. Volcanic boulders on the Makatea slope behind Te'autamatea. This
876 view is typical of the Vitaria Adze Quarry raw material procurement zones. E.
877 West is shown collecting geological sample 57. Photo by B. Rolett (June, 2000).

878

879 Figure 6. Chemical variations among samples from this study compared to
880 selected samples from the Austral Island region. Documented adze sources are
881 shown as gray-shaded fields as follows: Vitaria, Rurutu (this paper); Na'airoa,
882 Rurutu (Bollt, 2008), Ta'urama source, Rurutu (T) (Bollt, 2008), Tanataetea
883 (Tana), Tubuai (Hermann, 2013). Geological data for the Rurutu volcanics
884 (Rurutu Recent and Rurutu Old) are from Guille et al. (1998). The Vitaria source
885 is defined by artifacts and geological specimens collected at Vitaria. Seven
886 Peabody adzes (five from Rurutu, two from Raivavae) have compositions
887 consistent with the Vitaria source. Vitaria artifacts marked by inverted triangles
888 (with sample labels) are not consistent with the Vitaria source. Although RUR-46
889 could come from elsewhere on Rurutu, RUR-24 is unlike any known composition

890 on the island of Rurutu and was likely imported from off island. Two Peabody
891 benmoreite adzes with high SiO₂ (panel A) have less than 2 wt % MgO and < 1
892 wt % TiO₂, and plot outside the limits of the lower figure (B). Another sample
893 discussed in the text is adze C2365 from Aratika, Tuamotus (C) (Collerson and
894 Weisler, 2007). The trend of chemical data for Raivavae and Rapa is based on
895 data of Maury et al. (2013; In Press). Rock names are those of Le Bas et al.
896 (1986).

897

898 Figure 7.

899 Graphical representation of selected Peabody adze data compared to
900 compositional variation within the Vitaria source (quarry signature). The Vitaria
901 source (quarry signature) is calculated as the mean composition of all geological
902 and archeological samples from the Vitaria area (n=22, see Table 2) ±
903 uncertainty, where uncertainty is either one standard deviation from the mean or
904 analytical uncertainty, whichever is greater. See Sinton and Sinton (1997) for
905 analytical uncertainty values for the University of Hawai'i XRF system. Two
906 Peabody adzes collected on Raivavae (E36497 and E36496) have compositions
907 that plot within the uncertainty bounds of the Vitaria source (quarry signature) for
908 nearly all elements within analytical error. Thus, the two adzes collected on
909 Raivavae are chemically indistinguishable from Vitaria. Adze E36447, collected
910 on Tubuai, is significantly different from the Vitaria source in nearly all chemical
911 components.

912

913 Figure 8. Interisland transport of adzes in central East Polynesia, based on
914 geochemical evidence. Evidence supporting the source attributions varies and is
915 discussed in the text and cited references: Eiao to Mo'orea (Weisler, 1998); Eiao
916 to Tubuai (Hermann, 2013); Eiao to Rarotonga (McAlister et al., 2013); Raiatea
917 to Aitutaki (Allen and Johnson, 1997); Rurutu to Aratika (Collerson and Weisler,
918 2007); Rurutu to Mauke (this paper); Rurutu to Raivavae (this paper). Evidence
919 for the well-documented Southern Cooks interaction sphere (e.g., Allen and
920 Johnson, 1997; Sheppard and Walter, 1997; Weisler and Kirch, 1996; Walter and
921 Sheppard, 2001) is not depicted. Arrows depict direction of adze transport, but
922 are not intended to show specific navigational paths.

Table 1. Austral Islands Artifacts and Geological Specimens Selected for Geochemical Analysis

Island ^a :	Rurutu			Unaa	Tubuai	Raivavae	Total
District:	Te'autamatea ^b	Vitaria ^c	Vitaria ^d	R et al.	PEM	PEM	
Collector ^e :	R et al.	R et al.	PEM	R et al.	PEM	PEM	
Artifacts							
Finished adzes	-	-	1	-	2	7	10
Adze preforms	5	4	4	-	-	-	13
Large flakes	-	2	-	1	-	-	3
Cores	-	2	-	-	-	-	2
Debitage	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
Geological specimens							
Boulder outcrops	2	2	-	1	-	-	5
<i>Total</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>7</i>	35

a. Locations are find spots.

b. Te'autamatea, land area centered on Marae Tararoa (see Figure 3).

c. Locations in Vitaria District lying outside Te'autamatea (see Figure 2).

d. Unknown locations in Vitaria District.

e. Abbreviations: R et al., B. Rolett, E. West, J. Sinton, and R. Iovita; PEM, Peabody Essex Museum.

Table 2. Geochemical Compositional Data for Artifacts and Geological Samples Collected at Vitaria, Rurutu.

District Collected:	Vitaria																
Specimen:	10	14	16	26	27	31	36	38	40	48	52	55	57	60	61	62	66
Collector (1):	R et al.																
Specimen Type (2)	Ad pr	Fl	G	core	G	Ad pr	Ad pr	Ad pr	Ad pr	Db	G	core	G	Ad pr	Ad pr	Ad pr	Ad pr
Assigned Source:	Vitaria																
SiO ₂	46.96	46.63	46.70	46.81	47.35	47.47	47.07	47.14	47.03	46.96	47.48	46.91	46.90	47.00	46.72	47.13	47.16
TiO ₂	3.25	3.23	3.26	3.32	3.04	2.98	3.14	3.13	3.10	3.25	2.97	3.28	3.22	3.15	3.18	3.11	3.11
Al ₂ O ₃	16.08	15.98	16.15	15.93	16.22	16.29	16.09	16.12	16.01	16.26	16.17	16.38	16.01	16.11	15.92	16.13	16.06
FeO	13.70	13.57	13.74	13.79	13.32	13.34	13.44	13.54	13.39	13.87	13.26	13.67	13.58	13.53	13.56	13.41	13.34
MnO	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21
MgO	4.82	4.76	4.83	4.93	4.45	4.53	4.62	4.63	4.53	4.77	4.38	4.79	4.86	4.67	4.69	4.52	4.58
CaO	7.22	7.19	7.26	7.31	7.07	7.12	7.18	7.21	7.10	7.29	7.03	7.24	7.22	7.22	7.20	7.10	7.13
Na ₂ O	5.35	5.76	5.43	5.17	5.75	5.75	5.71	5.64	5.90	4.90	5.54	5.26	5.42	5.51	5.54	5.64	5.84
K ₂ O	1.59	1.60	1.58	1.54	1.67	1.65	1.63	1.61	1.64	1.55	1.68	1.59	1.64	1.59	1.57	1.61	1.64
P ₂ O ₅	1.03	1.05	1.05	1.01	1.15	1.16	1.10	1.10	1.11	1.09	1.16	1.04	1.03	1.10	1.09	1.11	1.09
Sum	100.21	100.00	100.22	100.03	100.25	100.51	100.19	100.32	100.02	100.17	99.88	100.38	100.09	100.08	99.69	99.97	100.17
Sc	9	11	10	12	8	8	10	9	9	11	9	10	9	9	9	8	10
V	120	139	137	140	109	111	131	115	114	131	122	127	126	131	133	122	135
Cr	-3	38	-3	-3	-3	3	-3	3	4	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3
Co	59	48	36	47	33	36	38	38	40	41	36	46	35	45	100	63	42
Ni	18	20	20	20	19	19	19	19	20	17	19	20	17	20	19	21	19
Cu																	
Zn	125	130	122	132	131	138	131	133	135	136	132	130	126	132	150	154	138
Rb	35	37	36	34	41	43	37	37	38	39	44	36	37	37	35	37	37
Sr	1192	1201	1215	1143	1282	1261	1242	1241	1238	1261	1279	1182	1194	1221	1216	1229	1211
Y	39	39	39	43	39	39	39	40	40	41	40	41	39	39	39	40	39
Zr	396	402	392	390	422	423	410	406	412	407	429	398	405	404	401	411	420
Nb	89	92	88	89	95	97	94	93	95	94	97	92	94	92	104	95	97
Ba	412	421	415	401	447	435	437	427	422	422	468	404	401	432	421	425	418
Pb	8	4	3	4	3	4	4	2	4	3	4	3	4	8	2	16	4
Th	9	9	8	9	9	8	9	8	9	8	9	9	9	9	8	8	9

1) Abbreviations: R et al., B. Rolett, J. Sinton, E. West, and R. Iovita; PEM, Peabody Essex Museum (M. Brunor). Proveniences for specimens collected by R et al. are plotted on Figures

2) Abbreviations: Ad, complete polished adze; Ad pr, adze preform; Db, debitage flake; Fl, large flake; G, geological.

Table 2. Geochemical Compositional Data for Artifacts and Geological Samples Collected at Vitaria, Rurutu.

continued

District Collected:	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria Quarry Averages					
Specimen:	E-49651C	E-49651G	E-41246G	E-41252A	E-41252D	<i>Geological</i>	<i>Artifacts</i>	<i>Combined</i>			
Collector (1):	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	<i>Average</i>	<i>St dev</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>St dev</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>St dev</i>
Specimen Type (2)	Ad pr	Ad	Ad pr	Ad pr	Ad pr	<i>n=4</i>		<i>n=18</i>		<i>n=22</i>	
Assigned Source:	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria						
SiO ₂	47.00	47.11	47.03	47.46	46.92	47.11	0.37	47.03	0.21	47.04	0.24
TiO ₂	3.12	3.09	3.11	3.07	3.15	3.12	0.14	3.15	0.08	3.15	0.09
Al ₂ O ₃	16.01	16.07	15.98	16.01	16.02	16.14	0.09	16.08	0.12	16.09	0.12
FeO	13.58	13.39	13.50	13.60	13.50	13.48	0.22	13.54	0.15	13.53	0.16
MnO	0.20	0.21	0.20	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.00	0.21	0.00	0.21	0.00
MgO	4.58	4.54	4.51	4.43	4.75	4.63	0.25	4.65	0.14	4.64	0.15
CaO	7.13	7.04	7.06	7.05	7.19	7.14	0.11	7.17	0.08	7.16	0.08
Na ₂ O	5.55	5.50	5.40	5.38	5.21	5.54	0.15	5.50	0.26	5.51	0.24
K ₂ O	1.60	1.66	1.66	1.58	1.58	1.65	0.05	1.61	0.04	1.61	0.04
P ₂ O ₅	1.09	1.07	1.07	1.11	1.08	1.09	0.07	1.08	0.03	1.08	0.04
Sum	99.86	99.68	99.52	99.88	99.59	100.11	0.17	100.01	0.27	100.03	0.26
Sc	11		10	12	9	9	1	10	1	10	1
V	119		110	102	110	123	11	123	11	123	11
Cr	13		23	6	3	-3	0	4	11	3	10
Co	88		75	58	57	35	1	54	18	51	18
Ni	22		19	21	20	19	1	20	1	19	1
Cu	20		28	25	26	0	0	25	3	25	3
Zn	137		136	138	132	128	5	136	7	134	7
Rb	37		44	38	36	39	3	37	2	38	3
Sr	1230		1213	1232	1253	1242	45	1221	30	1225	33
Y	39		39	39	39	39	1	40	1	39	1
Zr	403		418	416	409	412	17	407	9	408	10
Nb	114		114	105	104	94	4	98	8	97	7
Ba	410		405	430	413	433	30	420	11	422	16
Pb	5		9	6	9	4	1	6	3	5	3
Th	9		8	10	8	9	0	9	0	9	0

1) Abbreviations: R et al., B. Rolett, J. Sinton, E. West, and R. Iovita; PEM, Peabody Essex Museum (M. Brunor). Proveniences for specimens collected by R et al. are plotted on Figures 2 and

2) Abbreviations: Ad, complete polished adze; Ad pr, adze preform; Db, debitage flake; Fl, large flake; G, geological.

Table 3. Geochemical Compositional Data for Una'a Specimens and Data Outliers among Artifacts Collected at Vitaria, Rururtu.

	Vitaria: Data Outliers			Una'a Specimens	
	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Una'a	Una'a
District Collected:	Vitaria	Vitaria	Vitaria	Una'a	Una'a
Specimen:	46	24	E-49651B	2	3
Collector (1):	R et al.	R et al.	Peabody	R et al.	R et al.
Specimen Type (2)	Db	Fl	Ad pr	Fl	G
Assigned Source:	Una'a	unknown	unknown	Una'a	Una'a
SiO ₂	46.10	48.65	48.47	46.02	46.03
TiO ₂	3.58	2.36	2.62	3.63	3.58
Al ₂ O ₃	15.71	16.77	16.57	16.00	15.83
FeO*	14.10	12.17	12.69	14.12	14.30
MnO	0.21	0.24	0.20	0.23	0.21
MgO	5.41	3.30	3.93	4.87	5.47
CaO	7.55	6.71	6.77	7.68	7.61
Na ₂ O	5.04	6.60	5.74	5.42	4.71
K ₂ O	1.48	1.86	1.72	1.53	1.50
P ₂ O ₅	0.88	1.73	1.32	0.92	0.91
Sum	100.05	100.40	100.02	100.42	100.15
Sc	11	7	9		13
V	155	88	76		158
Cr	-3	-3	3		-3
Co	46	31	44		49
Ni	20	16	15		22
Cu			21		
Zn	127	154	145		128
Rb	32	48	41		31
Sr	1225	1544	1400		1099
Y	38	43	40		38
Zr	362	517	471		370
Nb	83	118	115		84
Ba	362	551	497		368
Pb	4	6	6		2
Th	8	12	11		7

1) Abbreviations: R et al., B. Rolett, J. Sinton, E. West, and R. Iovita; Peabody, Peabody Essex Museum (M. Brunor).

2) Abbreviations: Ad, complete polished adze; Ad pr, adze preform; Db,debitage flake; Fl, large flake; G, geological.

*Total Fe recorded as FeO.

Table

Table 4. Geochemical Compositional Data for Rurutu Quarry Averages and Selected Austral and Cook Islands Artifacts Collected on Raivavae, Tubuai, and Ma'uke

Island Collected:	Raivavae	Raivavae	Raivavae	Raivavae	Raivavae	Raivavae	Raivavae	Tubuai	Tubuai
Specimen:	E-36496	E-36497	E-33006	E-36512	E-36510	E-33009	E-36500	E-36447	E-36449
Artifact type (2):	Ad	Ad	Ad	Ad	Ad	Ad	Ad	Ad	Ad
Context:	surface	surface	surface	surface	surface	surface	surface	surface	surface
Collector (3):	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM	PEM
Assigned Source:	Rurutu Vitaria	Rurutu Vitaria	Rurutu or Tubuai	Rurutu or Tubuai	Raivavae?	Raivavae?	Raivavae?	Tubuai?	Tubuai?
SiO2	46.81	46.88	42.27	42.18	56.55	58.12	45.14	44.40	44.71
TiO2	3.09	3.09	4.28	4.50	0.91	0.56	4.05	3.58	3.09
Al2O3	16.02	16.11	14.89	15.39	18.00	16.81	14.73	16.06	14.63
FeO*	13.48	13.59	15.80	14.90	8.17	8.83	13.28	13.83	12.49
MnO	0.20	0.20	0.23	0.22	0.16	0.27	0.21	0.21	0.21
MgO	4.62	4.53	6.40	7.27	1.30	0.59	5.30	5.58	7.47
CaO	7.14	7.14	8.10	8.60	3.06	3.08	11.43	10.89	12.61
Na2O	5.53	5.64	4.79	4.37	5.11	7.01	2.93	3.56	3.21
K2O	1.60	1.57	1.66	1.70	5.47	3.31	1.76	1.13	1.01
P2O5	1.08	1.09	1.27	0.92	0.68	0.18	0.65	0.58	0.45
Sum	99.57	99.83	99.69	100.06	99.41	98.76	99.47	99.84	99.89
LOI	0.06	-0.16	0.16	-0.12	0.41	0.57	0.95	0.48	0.45
Sc		11	14	19		11	21	21	
V		111	209	248		-3	313	327	
Cr		7	9	11		-3	34	13	
Co		70	74	85		87	81	88	
Ni		20	48	79		15	68	47	
Cu		29	78	76		7	107	87	
Zn		135	158	130		195	130	128	
Rb		35	39	35		128	40	27	
Sr		1234	1060	954		304	816	938	
Y		39	39	35		52	34	31	
Zr		403	427	357		1083	350	239	
Nb		107	110	97		143	65	91	
Ba		412	373	329		439	415	355	
Pb		10	6	5		16	19	5	
Th		9	9	6		17	4	6	

Table 4. Geochemical Compositional Data for Rurutu Quarry Averages and Selected Austral and Cook Islands Artifacts Collected on Raivavae, Tubuai, and Ma'uke

continued

Island Collected:	Ma'uke	Ma'uke	Rurutu Quarry Averages (1)		
Specimen:	RW-G	RW-E	Combinec	Combinec	Combined
Artifact type (2):	C	Ad	Average	Average	Average
Context:	<i>in situ</i>	<i>in situ</i>	<i>n=22</i>	<i>n=6</i>	<i>n=3</i>
Collector (3):	Walter	Walter			
Assigned Source:	Rurutu	Rurutu	Rurutu	Rurutu	Rurutu
			Vitaria	Na'a'iroa	Ta'urama
SiO ₂	42.16	42.30	47.04	42.42	43.07
TiO ₂	4.34	4.33	3.15	4.32	4.60
Al ₂ O ₃	14.67	14.79	16.09	15.03	15.63
FeO*	15.81	15.54	13.53	15.77	13.43
MnO	0.28	0.27	0.21	0.22	0.20
MgO	6.47	6.52	4.64	6.47	7.55
CaO	8.39	8.31	7.16	8.18	8.92
Na ₂ O	4.41	4.86	5.51	4.80	4.18
K ₂ O	1.73	1.70	1.61	1.70	1.69
P ₂ O ₅	1.24	1.22	1.08	1.31	0.97
Sum	99.50	99.84	100.03	100.23	100.26
LOI	0.75	0.29			
Sc			10	12	17
V			123	203	250
Cr			3		
Co			51	5	46
Ni			19	45	73
Cu			25		
Zn			134	163	140
Rb			38	43	36
Sr			1225	1094	1030
Y			39	40	37
Zr			408	439	366
Nb			97	106	88
Ba			422	419	370
Pb			5	8	3
Th			9		5

Figure

Map created by Scott F. Allen

Map source: OpenStreetMap

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Data source: Barry Rolett
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